
p-adic Ghobber-Jaming Uncertainty Principle

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Abstract: Let $\{\tau_j\}_{j=1}^n$ and $\{\omega_k\}_{k=1}^n$ be two orthonormal bases for a finite dimensional p-adic Hilbert space \mathcal{X} . Let $M, N \subseteq \{1, \dots, n\}$ be such that

$$\max_{j \in M, k \in N} |\langle \tau_j, \omega_k \rangle| < 1,$$

where $o(M)$ is the cardinality of M . Then for all $x \in \mathcal{X}$, we show that

$$(1) \quad \|x\| \leq \left(\frac{1}{1 - \max_{j \in M, k \in N} |\langle \tau_j, \omega_k \rangle|} \right) \max \left\{ \max_{j \in M^c} |\langle x, \tau_j \rangle|, \max_{k \in N^c} |\langle x, \omega_k \rangle| \right\}.$$

We call Inequality (1) as **p-adic Ghobber-Jaming Uncertainty Principle**. Inequality (1) is the p-adic version of uncertainty principle obtained by Ghobber and Jaming [*Linear Algebra Appl.*, 2011]. We also derive analogues of Inequality (1) for non-Archimedean Banach spaces.

Keywords: Uncertainty Principle, Orthonormal Basis, p-adic Hilbert space, non-Archimedean Banach space.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Let $d \in \mathbb{N}$ and $\widehat{\cdot}: \mathcal{L}^2(\mathbb{R}^d) \rightarrow \mathcal{L}^2(\mathbb{R}^d)$ be the unitary Fourier transform obtained by extending uniquely the bounded linear operator

$$\widehat{\cdot}: \mathcal{L}^1(\mathbb{R}^d) \cap \mathcal{L}^2(\mathbb{R}^d) \ni f \mapsto \widehat{f} \in C_0(\mathbb{R}^d); \quad \widehat{f}: \mathbb{R}^d \ni \xi \mapsto \widehat{f}(\xi) := \int_{\mathbb{R}^d} f(x) e^{-2\pi i \langle x, \xi \rangle} dx \in \mathbb{C}.$$

In 2007, Jaming [6] extended the uncertainty principle obtained by Nazarov for \mathbb{R} in 1993 [12] (cf. [5]). In the following theorem, Lebesgue measure on \mathbb{R}^d is denoted by m . Mean width of a measurable subset E of \mathbb{R}^d having finite measure is denoted by $w(E)$.

Theorem 1.1. [6, 12] (*Nazarov-Jaming Uncertainty Principle*) For each $d \in \mathbb{N}$, there exists a universal constant C_d (depends upon d) satisfying the following: If $E, F \subseteq \mathbb{R}^d$ are measurable subsets having finite measure, then for all $f \in \mathcal{L}^2(\mathbb{R}^d)$,

$$\int_{\mathbb{R}^d} |f(x)|^2 dx \leq C_d e^{C_d \min\{m(E)m(F), m(E)^{\frac{1}{d}}w(F), m(F)^{\frac{1}{d}}w(E)\}} \left[\int_{E^c} |f(x)|^2 dx + \int_{F^c} |\widehat{f}(\xi)|^2 d\xi \right].$$

In particular, if f is supported on E and \widehat{f} is supported on F , then $f = 0$.

In 2011, Ghobber and Jaming derived the following finite dimensional version of Theorem 1.1. Given a subset $M \subseteq \{1, \dots, n\}$, the number of elements in M is denoted by $o(M)$.

Theorem 1.2. [4] (*Ghobber-Jaming Uncertainty Principle*) Let $\{\tau_j\}_{j=1}^n$ and $\{\omega_j\}_{j=1}^n$ be orthonormal bases for the Hilbert space \mathbb{C}^n . If $M, N \subseteq \{1, \dots, n\}$ are such that

$$o(M)o(N) < \frac{1}{\max_{1 \leq j, k \leq n} |\langle \tau_j, \omega_k \rangle|^2},$$

then for all $h \in \mathbb{C}^n$,

$$\|h\| \leq \left(1 + \frac{1}{1 - \sqrt{o(M)o(N)} \max_{1 \leq j, k \leq n} |\langle \tau_j, \omega_k \rangle|} \right) \left[\left(\sum_{j \in M^c} |\langle h, \tau_j \rangle|^2 \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} + \left(\sum_{k \in N^c} |\langle h, \omega_k \rangle|^2 \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \right].$$

In particular, if h is supported on M in the expansion using basis $\{\tau_j\}_{j=1}^n$ and h is supported on N in the expansion using basis $\{\omega_j\}_{j=1}^n$, then $h = 0$.

Recently, Theorem 1.2 has been extended to Banach spaces using the notion of p-orthonormal bases.

Theorem 1.3. [11] (*Functional Ghobber-Jaming Uncertainty Principle*) Let $(\{f_j\}_{j=1}^n, \{\tau_j\}_{j=1}^n)$ and $(\{g_k\}_{k=1}^n, \{\omega_k\}_{k=1}^n)$ be p-orthonormal bases for a finite dimensional Banach space \mathcal{X} . If $M, N \subseteq \{1, \dots, n\}$ are such that

$$o(M)^{\frac{1}{q}} o(N)^{\frac{1}{p}} < \frac{1}{\max_{1 \leq j, k \leq n} |g_k(\tau_j)|},$$

then for all $x \in \mathcal{X}$,

$$\|x\| \leq \left(1 + \frac{1}{1 - o(M)^{\frac{1}{q}} o(N)^{\frac{1}{p}} \max_{1 \leq j, k \leq n} |g_k(\tau_j)|} \right) \left[\left(\sum_{j \in M^c} |f_j(x)|^p \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} + \left(\sum_{k \in N^c} |g_k(x)|^p \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \right].$$

In particular, if x is supported on M in the expansion using basis $\{\tau_j\}_{j=1}^n$ and x is supported on N in the expansion using basis $\{\omega_k\}_{k=1}^n$, then $x = 0$.

It is reasonable to ask whether there are p-adic (non-Archimedean) versions of Theorems 1.2 and 1.3? We are going to answer this question in the paper.

2. P-ADIC GHOBBER-JAMING UNCERTAINTY PRINCIPLE

We begin by recalling the notion of p-adic Hilbert space.

Definition 2.1. [7] Let \mathbb{K} be a non-Archimedean valued field with valuation $|\cdot|$ and \mathcal{X} be a non-Archimedean Banach space with norm $\|\cdot\|$ over \mathbb{K} . We say that \mathcal{X} is a **p-adic Hilbert space** if there is a map (called as p-adic inner product) $\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle : \mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathbb{K}$ satisfying following.

- (i) If $x \in \mathcal{X}$ is such that $\langle x, y \rangle = 0$ for all $y \in \mathcal{X}$, then $x = 0$.
- (ii) $\langle x, y \rangle = \langle y, x \rangle$ for all $x, y \in \mathcal{X}$.
- (iii) $\langle \alpha x + y, z \rangle = \alpha \langle x, z \rangle + \langle y, z \rangle$ for all $\alpha \in \mathbb{K}$, for all $x, y, z \in \mathcal{X}$.
- (iv) $|\langle x, y \rangle| \leq \|x\| \|y\|$ for all $x, y \in \mathcal{X}$.

The following is the standard example of a p-adic Hilbert space.

Example 2.2. [7] Let p be a prime. For $d \in \mathbb{N}$, let \mathbb{Q}_p^d be the standard p -adic Hilbert space equipped with the inner product

$$\langle (a_j)_{j=1}^d, (b_j)_{j=1}^d \rangle := \sum_{j=1}^d a_j b_j, \quad \forall (a_j)_{j=1}^d, (b_j)_{j=1}^d \in \mathbb{Q}_p^d$$

and the norm

$$\|(x_j)_{j=1}^d\| := \max_{1 \leq j \leq d} |x_j|, \quad \forall (x_j)_{j=1}^d \in \mathbb{Q}_p^d.$$

In the paper, we use the following notion of orthonormal basis for p -adic Hilbert spaces.

Definition 2.3. Let \mathcal{X} be a p -adic Hilbert space over \mathbb{K} . A basis $\{\tau_j\}_{j=1}^n$ for \mathcal{X} is said to be an orthonormal basis for \mathcal{X} if the following conditions hold.

- (i) $\|\tau_j\| \leq 1$ for all $1 \leq j \leq n$.
- (ii) $\langle \tau_j, \tau_k \rangle = \delta_{j,k}$ for all $1 \leq j, k \leq n$.

Given an orthonormal basis $\{\tau_j\}_{j=1}^n$ for \mathcal{X} , we have following.

- (i) For every $x \in \mathcal{X}$,

$$\text{(p-adic Fourier expansion)} \quad x = \sum_{j=1}^n \langle x, \tau_j \rangle \tau_j.$$

- (ii) For every $x \in \mathcal{X}$,

$$\text{(p-adic Parseval formula for norm)} \quad \|x\| = \max_{1 \leq j \leq n} |\langle x, \tau_j \rangle|.$$

- (iii) For every $x, y \in \mathcal{X}$,

$$\text{(p-adic Parseval formula for inner product)} \quad \langle x, y \rangle = \sum_{j=1}^n \langle x, \tau_j \rangle \langle \tau_j, y \rangle.$$

- (iv) For every $(a_j)_{j=1}^n \in \mathbb{K}^n$,

$$\left\| \sum_{j=1}^n a_j \tau_j \right\| = \max_{1 \leq j \leq n} |a_j|.$$

Let \mathcal{X} be a p -adic Hilbert space. Recall that a linear operator $T : \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathcal{X}$ is said to be an isometry if $\|Tx\| = \|x\|$ for all $x \in \mathcal{X}$. An invertible isometry $T : \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathcal{X}$ is said to be unitary if $\langle Tx, Ty \rangle = \langle x, y \rangle$ for all $x, y \in \mathcal{X}$. Note that unlike real or complex Hilbert spaces, neither

$$\langle Tx, Ty \rangle = \langle x, y \rangle, \quad \forall x, y \in \mathcal{X} \quad \not\Rightarrow \quad \|Tx\| = \|x\|, \quad \forall x \in \mathcal{X}$$

nor

$$\|Tx\| = \|x\|, \quad \forall x \in \mathcal{X} \quad \not\Rightarrow \quad \langle Tx, Ty \rangle = \langle x, y \rangle, \quad \forall x, y \in \mathcal{X}.$$

In the next result we characterize all orthonormal bases for a given p -adic Hilbert space.

Theorem 2.4. Let $\{\tau_j\}_{j=1}^n$ be an orthonormal basis for \mathcal{X} . Then a collection $\{\omega_j\}_{j=1}^n$ in \mathcal{X} is an orthonormal basis for \mathcal{X} if and only if there is a unitary $V : \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathcal{X}$ such that

$$\omega_j = V\tau_j, \quad \forall 1 \leq j \leq n.$$

Proof. (\Rightarrow) Define $V : \mathcal{X} \ni x \mapsto \sum_{j=1}^n \langle x, \tau_j \rangle \omega_j \in \mathcal{X}$. Since $\{\omega_j\}_{j=1}^n$ is a basis for \mathcal{X} , V is invertible with inverse $V^{-1} : \mathcal{X} \ni x \mapsto \sum_{j=1}^n \langle x, \omega_j \rangle \tau_j \in \mathcal{X}$. For $x \in \mathcal{X}$,

$$\|Vx\| = \left\| \sum_{j=1}^n \langle x, \tau_j \rangle \omega_j \right\| = \max_{1 \leq j \leq n} |\langle x, \tau_j \rangle| = \|x\|.$$

Therefore V is an isometry. For $x, y \in \mathcal{X}$,

$$\langle Vx, Vy \rangle = \left\langle \sum_{j=1}^n \langle x, \tau_j \rangle \omega_j, \sum_{k=1}^n \langle y, \tau_k \rangle \omega_k \right\rangle = \sum_{j=1}^n \langle x, \tau_j \rangle \langle \tau_j, y \rangle = \langle x, y \rangle.$$

Therefore V is a unitary. We clearly have $\omega_j = V\tau_j, \forall 1 \leq j \leq n$.

(\Leftarrow) Since V is invertible, $\{\omega_j\}_{j=1}^n$ is a basis for \mathcal{X} . Since V is an isometry, we have $\|\omega_j\| = \|\tau_j\| \leq 1$ for all $1 \leq j \leq n$. Since V is unitary, we have

$$\langle \omega_j, \omega_k \rangle = \langle V\tau_j, V\tau_k \rangle = \langle \tau_j, \tau_k \rangle = \delta_{j,k}, \quad \forall 1 \leq j, k \leq n.$$

□

Now we derive p-adic version of Theorem 1.2.

Theorem 2.5. (*p-adic Ghobber-Jaming Uncertainty Principle*) Let \mathcal{X} be a finite dimensional p-adic Hilbert space over \mathbb{K} . Let $\{\tau_j\}_{j=1}^n$ and $\{\omega_k\}_{k=1}^n$ be two orthonormal bases for \mathcal{X} . If $M, N \subseteq \{1, \dots, n\}$ are such that

$$\max_{j \in M, k \in N} |\langle \tau_j, \omega_k \rangle| < 1,$$

then for all $x \in \mathcal{X}$,

$$(2) \quad \|x\| \leq \left(\frac{1}{1 - \max_{j \in M, k \in N} |\langle \tau_j, \omega_k \rangle|} \right) \max \left\{ \max_{j \in M^c} |\langle x, \tau_j \rangle|, \max_{k \in N^c} |\langle x, \omega_k \rangle| \right\}.$$

In particular, if x is supported on M in the expansion using basis $\{\tau_j\}_{j=1}^n$ and x is supported on N in the expansion using basis $\{\omega_j\}_{j=1}^n$, then $x = 0$.

Proof. Given $S \subseteq \{1, \dots, n\}$, define

$$\begin{aligned} P_S x &:= \sum_{j \in S} \langle x, \tau_j \rangle \tau_j, \quad \forall x \in \mathcal{X}, \\ \|x\|_{S, \tau} &:= \max_{j \in S} |\langle x, \tau_j \rangle|, \quad \forall x \in \mathcal{X}, \\ \|x\|_{S, \omega} &:= \max_{k \in S} |\langle x, \omega_k \rangle|, \quad \forall x \in \mathcal{X}. \end{aligned}$$

Then

$$\|P_S x\| = \left\| \sum_{j \in S} \langle x, \tau_j \rangle \tau_j \right\| = \max_{j \in S} |\langle x, \tau_j \rangle| = \|x\|_{S, \tau}, \quad \forall x \in \mathcal{X}.$$

Define $V : \mathcal{X} \ni x \mapsto \sum_{k=1}^n \langle x, \omega_k \rangle \tau_k \in \mathcal{X}$. Then V is an invertible isometry. Using V we have

$$\begin{aligned} \|P_S Vx\| &= \left\| \sum_{j \in S} \langle Vx, \tau_j \rangle \tau_j \right\| = \max_{j \in S} |\langle Vx, \tau_j \rangle| = \max_{j \in S} \left| \left\langle \sum_{k=1}^n \langle x, \omega_k \rangle \tau_k, \tau_j \right\rangle \right| \\ &= \max_{j \in S} |\langle x, \omega_j \rangle| = \|x\|_{S, \omega}, \quad \forall x \in \mathcal{X}. \end{aligned}$$

For $x \in \mathcal{X}$, we now find

$$\begin{aligned}
\|P_N V P_M x\| &= \left\| \sum_{k \in N} \langle V P_M x, \tau_k \rangle \tau_k \right\| = \max_{k \in N} |\langle V P_M x, \tau_k \rangle| \\
&= \max_{k \in N} \left| \left\langle V \left(\sum_{j \in M} \langle x, \tau_j \rangle \tau_j \right), \tau_k \right\rangle \right| = \max_{k \in N} \left| \left\langle \sum_{j \in M} \langle x, \tau_j \rangle V \tau_j, \tau_k \right\rangle \right| \\
&= \max_{k \in N} \left| \sum_{j \in M} \langle x, \tau_j \rangle \langle V \tau_j, \tau_k \rangle \right| = \max_{k \in N} \left| \sum_{j \in M} \langle x, \tau_j \rangle \left\langle \sum_{r=1}^n \langle \tau_j, \omega_r \rangle \tau_r, \tau_k \right\rangle \right| \\
&= \max_{k \in N} \left| \sum_{j \in M} \langle x, \tau_j \rangle \langle \tau_j, \omega_k \rangle \right| \leq \max_{k \in N} \max_{j \in M} |\langle x, \tau_j \rangle \langle \tau_j, \omega_k \rangle| \\
&\leq \left(\max_{j \in M, k \in N} |\langle \tau_j, \omega_k \rangle| \right) \max_{j \in M} |\langle x, \tau_j \rangle| \leq \left(\max_{j \in M, k \in N} |\langle \tau_j, \omega_k \rangle| \right) \|x\|.
\end{aligned}$$

Therefore

$$(3) \quad \|P_N V P_M\| \leq \max_{j \in M, k \in N} |\langle \tau_j, \omega_k \rangle|.$$

Now let $y \in \mathcal{X}$ be such that $\{j \in \{1, \dots, n\} : \langle y, \tau_j \rangle \neq 0\} \subseteq M$. Then

$$\|P_N V y\| = \|P_N V P_M y\| \leq \|P_N V P_M\| \|y\|$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}
\|y\|_{N^c, \omega} &= \|P_{N^c} V y\| = \|V y - P_N V y\| \\
&\geq \|V y\| - \|P_N V y\| = \|y\| - \|P_N V y\| \\
&\geq \|y\| - \|P_N V P_M\| \|y\|.
\end{aligned}$$

Therefore

$$(4) \quad \|y\|_{N^c, \omega} \geq (1 - \|P_N V P_M\|) \|y\|.$$

Let $x \in \mathcal{X}$. Note that $P_M x$ satisfies $\{j \in \{1, \dots, n\} : \langle P_M x, \tau_j \rangle \neq 0\} \subseteq M$. Now using (3) and (4) we get

$$\begin{aligned}
\|x\| &= \|P_{M^c}x + P_Mx\| \leq \max\{\|P_{M^c}x\|, \|P_Mx\|\} \\
&\leq \max\left\{\|P_{M^c}x\|, \frac{1}{1 - \|P_NVP_M\|} \|P_Mx\|_{N^c, \omega}\right\} \\
&= \max\left\{\|P_{M^c}x\|, \frac{1}{1 - \|P_NVP_M\|} \|P_{N^c}VP_Mx\|\right\} \\
&= \max\left\{\|P_{M^c}x\|, \frac{1}{1 - \|P_NVP_M\|} \|P_{N^c}V(x - P_{M^c}x)\|\right\} \\
&\leq \max\left\{\|P_{M^c}x\|, \frac{1}{1 - \|P_NVP_M\|} \|P_{N^c}Vx\|, \frac{1}{1 - \|P_NVP_M\|} \|P_{N^c}VP_{M^c}x\|\right\} \\
&\leq \max\left\{\|P_{M^c}x\|, \frac{1}{1 - \|P_NVP_M\|} \|P_{N^c}Vx\|, \frac{1}{1 - \|P_NVP_M\|} \|P_{M^c}x\|\right\} \\
&= \max\left\{\frac{1}{1 - \|P_NVP_M\|} \|P_{M^c}x\|, \frac{1}{1 - \|P_NVP_M\|} \|P_{N^c}Vx\|\right\} \\
&= \left(\frac{1}{1 - \|P_NVP_M\|}\right) \max\{\|P_{M^c}x\|, \|P_{N^c}Vx\|\} \\
&= \left(\frac{1}{1 - \|P_NVP_M\|}\right) \max\{\|x\|_{M^c, \tau}, \|x\|_{N^c, \omega}\} \\
&= \left(\frac{1}{1 - \|P_NVP_M\|}\right) \max\left\{\max_{j \in M^c} |\langle x, \tau_j \rangle|, \max_{k \in N^c} |\langle x, \omega_k \rangle|\right\} \\
&\leq \left(\frac{1}{1 - \max_{j \in M, k \in N} |\langle \tau_j, \omega_k \rangle|}\right) \max\left\{\max_{j \in M^c} |\langle x, \tau_j \rangle|, \max_{k \in N^c} |\langle x, \omega_k \rangle|\right\}.
\end{aligned}$$

□

3. NON-ARCHIMEDEAN GHOBBER-JAMING UNCERTAINTY PRINCIPLE

We now want to derive Ghobber-Jaming uncertainty principle for non-Archimedean Banach spaces. For this, we introduce the following notion of orthonormal bases.

Definition 3.1. *Let \mathcal{X} be a finite dimensional non-Archimedean Banach space over \mathbb{K} . Let $\{\tau_j\}_{j=1}^n$ be a basis for \mathcal{X} and let $\{f_j\}_{j=1}^n$ be the coordinate functionals associated with $\{\tau_j\}_{j=1}^n$. The pair $(\{f_j\}_{j=1}^n, \{\tau_j\}_{j=1}^n)$ is said to be an **orthonormal basis** for \mathcal{X} if the following conditions hold.*

- (i) $\|\tau_j\| \leq 1$ for all $1 \leq j \leq n$.
- (ii) $\|f_j\| \leq 1$ for all $1 \leq j \leq n$.

Given an orthonormal basis $(\{f_j\}_{j=1}^n, \{\tau_j\}_{j=1}^n)$ for \mathcal{X} , we have following.

- (i) For every $x \in \mathcal{X}$,

$$\text{(Non-Archimedean basis expansion)} \quad x = \sum_{j=1}^n f_j(x) \tau_j.$$

- (ii) For every $x \in \mathcal{X}$,

$$\text{(Non-Archimedean Parseval formula for norm)} \quad \|x\| = \max_{1 \leq j \leq n} |f_j(x)|.$$

(iii) For every linear functional $\phi : \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathbb{K}$,

$$\phi = \sum_{j=1}^n \phi(\tau_j) f_j.$$

(iv) For every linear functional $\phi : \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathbb{K}$,

$$\|\phi\| = \max_{1 \leq j \leq n} |\phi(\tau_j)|.$$

(v) For every $(a_j)_{j=1}^n, (b_j)_{j=1}^n \in \mathbb{K}^n$,

$$\left\| \sum_{j=1}^n a_j \tau_j \right\| = \max_{1 \leq j \leq n} |a_j| \quad \text{and} \quad \left\| \sum_{j=1}^n b_j f_j \right\| = \max_{1 \leq j \leq n} |b_j|.$$

In the next result we characterize all orthonormal bases for a given non-Archimedean Banach space.

Theorem 3.2. *Let $(\{f_j\}_{j=1}^n, \{\tau_j\}_{j=1}^n)$ be an orthonormal basis for \mathcal{X} . Then a pair $(\{g_j\}_{j=1}^n, \{\omega_j\}_{j=1}^n)$ is an orthonormal basis for \mathcal{X} if and only if there is an invertible linear isometry $V : \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathcal{X}$ such that*

$$g_j = f_j V^{-1}, \quad \omega_j = V \tau_j, \quad \forall 1 \leq j \leq n.$$

Proof. (\Rightarrow) Define $V : \mathcal{X} \ni x \mapsto \sum_{j=1}^n f_j(x) \omega_j \in \mathcal{X}$. Since $\{\omega_j\}_{j=1}^n$ is a basis for \mathcal{X} , V is invertible with inverse $V^{-1} : \mathcal{X} \ni x \mapsto \sum_{j=1}^n g_j(x) \tau_j \in \mathcal{X}$. For $x \in \mathcal{X}$,

$$\|Vx\| = \left\| \sum_{j=1}^n f_j(x) \omega_j \right\| = \max_{1 \leq j \leq n} |f_j(x)| = \|x\|.$$

Therefore V is an isometry. Note that we clearly have $\omega_j = V \tau_j, \forall 1 \leq j \leq n$. Now let $1 \leq j \leq n$. Then

$$f_j(V^{-1}x) = f_j \left(\sum_{k=1}^n g_k(x) \tau_k \right) = \sum_{k=1}^n g_k(x) f_j(\tau_k) = g_j(x), \quad \forall x \in \mathcal{X}.$$

(\Leftarrow) Since V is invertible, $\{\omega_j\}_{j=1}^n$ is a basis for \mathcal{X} . Now we see that $g_j(\omega_k) = f_j(V^{-1}V\tau_k) = f_j(\tau_k) = \delta_{j,k}$ for all $1 \leq j, k \leq n$. Therefore $\{g_j\}_{j=1}^n$ is the coordinate functionals associated with $\{\omega_j\}_{j=1}^n$. Since V is an isometry, we have $\|\omega_j\| = \|\tau_j\| \leq 1$ for all $1 \leq j \leq n$. Since V is also invertible, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \|g_j\| &= \sup_{x \in \mathcal{X} \setminus \{0\}} \frac{|g_j(x)|}{\|x\|} = \sup_{x \in \mathcal{X} \setminus \{0\}} \frac{|f_j(V^{-1}x)|}{\|x\|} = \sup_{y \in \mathcal{X} \setminus \{0\}} \frac{|f_j(y)|}{\|Vy\|} \\ &= \sup_{y \in \mathcal{X} \setminus \{0\}} \frac{|f_j(y)|}{\|y\|} = \|f_j\| \leq 1, \quad \forall 1 \leq j \leq n. \end{aligned}$$

□

We now derive non-Archimedean version of Theorem 1.3.

Theorem 3.3. (*Non-Archimedean Ghobber-Jaming Uncertainty Principle*) *Let \mathcal{X} be a finite dimensional non-Archimedean Banach space over \mathbb{K} . Let $(\{f_j\}_{j=1}^n, \{\tau_j\}_{j=1}^n)$ and $(\{g_k\}_{k=1}^n, \{\omega_k\}_{k=1}^n)$ be orthonormal bases for \mathcal{X} . If $M, N \subseteq \{1, \dots, n\}$ are such that*

$$\max_{j \in M, k \in N} |g_k(\tau_j)| < 1,$$

then for all $x \in \mathcal{X}$,

$$(5) \quad \|x\| \leq \left(\frac{1}{1 - \max_{j \in M, k \in N} |g_k(\tau_j)|} \right) \max \left\{ \max_{j \in M^c} |f_j(x)|, \max_{k \in N^c} |g_k(x)| \right\}.$$

In particular, if x is supported on M in the expansion using basis $(\{f_j\}_{j=1}^n, \{\tau_j\}_{j=1}^n)$ and x is supported on N in the expansion using basis $(\{g_k\}_{k=1}^n, \{\omega_k\}_{k=1}^n)$, then $x = 0$.

Proof. Given $S \subseteq \{1, \dots, n\}$, define

$$\begin{aligned} P_S x &:= \sum_{j \in S} f_j(x) \tau_j, \quad \forall x \in \mathcal{X}, \\ \|x\|_{S,f} &:= \max_{j \in S} |f_j(x)|, \quad \forall x \in \mathcal{X}, \\ \|x\|_{S,g} &:= \max_{j \in S} |g_j(x)|, \quad \forall x \in \mathcal{X}. \end{aligned}$$

Then

$$\|P_S x\| = \left\| \sum_{j \in S} f_j(x) \tau_j \right\| = \max_{j \in S} |f_j(x)| = \|x\|_{S,f}, \quad \forall x \in \mathcal{X}.$$

Define $V : \mathcal{X} \ni x \mapsto \sum_{k=1}^n g_k(x) \tau_k \in \mathcal{X}$. Then V is an invertible isometry. Using V we get

$$\begin{aligned} \|P_S V x\| &= \left\| \sum_{j \in S} f_j(V x) \tau_j \right\| = \left\| \sum_{j \in S} f_j \left(\sum_{k=1}^n g_k(x) \tau_k \right) \tau_j \right\| = \left\| \sum_{j \in S} \sum_{k=1}^n g_k(x) f_j(\tau_k) \tau_j \right\| \\ &= \left\| \sum_{j \in S} g_j(x) \tau_j \right\| = \max_{j \in S} |g_j(x)| = \|x\|_{S,g}, \quad \forall x \in \mathcal{X}. \end{aligned}$$

For $x \in \mathcal{X}$, we now find

$$\begin{aligned} \|P_N V P_M x\| &= \left\| \sum_{k \in N} f_k(V P_M x) \tau_k \right\| = \max_{k \in N} |f_k(V P_M x)| \\ &= \max_{k \in N} \left| (f_k V) \left(\sum_{j \in M} f_j(x) \tau_j \right) \right| = \max_{k \in N} \left| \sum_{j \in M} f_j(x) f_k(V \tau_j) \right| \\ &= \max_{k \in N} \left| \sum_{j \in M} f_j(x) f_k \left(\sum_{r=1}^n g_r(\tau_j) \tau_r \right) \right| = \max_{k \in N} \left| \sum_{j \in M} f_j(x) \sum_{r=1}^n g_r(\tau_j) f_k(\tau_r) \right| \\ &= \max_{k \in N} \left| \sum_{j \in M} f_j(x) g_k(\tau_j) \right| \leq \max_{k \in N} \max_{j \in M} |f_j(x) g_k(\tau_j)| \\ &\leq \left(\max_{j \in M, k \in N} |g_k(\tau_j)| \right) \max_{j \in M} |f_j(x)| \leq \left(\max_{j \in M, k \in N} |g_k(\tau_j)| \right) \|x\|. \end{aligned}$$

So we have

$$(6) \quad \|P_N V P_M\| \leq \max_{j \in M, k \in N} |g_k(\tau_j)|.$$

Now let $y \in \mathcal{X}$ be such that $\{j \in \{1, \dots, n\} : f_j(y) \neq 0\} \subseteq M$. Then

$$\|P_N V y\| = \|P_N V P_M y\| \leq \|P_N V P_M\| \|y\|$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \|y\|_{N^c, g} &= \|P_{N^c} V y\| = \|V y - P_N V y\| \\ &\geq \|V y\| - \|P_N V y\| = \|y\| - \|P_N V y\| \\ &\geq \|y\| - \|P_N V P_M\| \|y\|. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore

$$(7) \quad \|y\|_{N^c, g} \geq (1 - \|P_N V P_M\|) \|y\|.$$

Let $x \in \mathcal{X}$. Note that $P_M x$ satisfies $\{j \in \{1, \dots, n\} : f_j(P_M x) \neq 0\} \subseteq M$. Now using (6) and (7) we get

$$\begin{aligned} \|x\| &= \|P_{M^c} x + P_M x\| \leq \max\{\|P_{M^c} x\|, \|P_M x\|\} \\ &\leq \max\left\{\|P_{M^c} x\|, \frac{1}{1 - \|P_N V P_M\|} \|P_M x\|_{N^c, g}\right\} \\ &= \max\left\{\|P_{M^c} x\|, \frac{1}{1 - \|P_N V P_M\|} \|P_{N^c} V P_M x\|\right\} \\ &= \max\left\{\|P_{M^c} x\|, \frac{1}{1 - \|P_N V P_M\|} \|P_{N^c} V(x - P_{M^c} x)\|\right\} \\ &\leq \max\left\{\|P_{M^c} x\|, \frac{1}{1 - \|P_N V P_M\|} \|P_{N^c} V x\|, \frac{1}{1 - \|P_N V P_M\|} \|P_{N^c} V P_{M^c} x\|\right\} \\ &\leq \max\left\{\|P_{M^c} x\|, \frac{1}{1 - \|P_N V P_M\|} \|P_{N^c} V x\|, \frac{1}{1 - \|P_N V P_M\|} \|P_{M^c} x\|\right\} \\ &= \max\left\{\frac{1}{1 - \|P_N V P_M\|} \|P_{M^c} x\|, \frac{1}{1 - \|P_N V P_M\|} \|P_{N^c} V x\|\right\} \\ &= \left(\frac{1}{1 - \|P_N V P_M\|}\right) \max\{\|P_{M^c} x\|, \|P_{N^c} V x\|\} \\ &= \left(\frac{1}{1 - \|P_N V P_M\|}\right) \max\{\|x\|_{M^c, f}, \|x\|_{N^c, g}\} \\ &= \left(\frac{1}{1 - \|P_N V P_M\|}\right) \max\left\{\max_{j \in M^c} |f_j(x)|, \max_{k \in N^c} |g_k(x)|\right\} \\ &\leq \left(\frac{1}{1 - \max_{j \in M, k \in N} |g_k(\tau_j)|}\right) \max\left\{\max_{j \in M^c} |f_j(x)|, \max_{k \in N^c} |g_k(x)|\right\}. \end{aligned}$$

□

By interchanging orthonormal bases in Theorem 3.3 we get the following theorem.

Theorem 3.4. (Non-Archimedean Ghobber-Jaming Uncertainty Principle) *Let \mathcal{X} be a finite dimensional non-Archimedean Banach space over \mathbb{K} . Let $(\{f_j\}_{j=1}^n, \{\tau_j\}_{j=1}^n)$ and $(\{g_k\}_{k=1}^n, \{\omega_k\}_{k=1}^n)$ be orthonormal bases for \mathcal{X} . If $M, N \subseteq \{1, \dots, n\}$ are such that*

$$\max_{j \in M, k \in N} |f_j(\omega_k)| < 1,$$

then for all $x \in \mathcal{X}$,

$$\|x\| \leq \left(\frac{1}{1 - \max_{j \in M, k \in N} |f_j(\omega_k)|} \right) \max \left\{ \max_{k \in M^c} |g_k(x)|, \max_{j \in N^c} |f_j(x)| \right\}.$$

In particular, if x is supported on M in the expansion using basis $(\{f_j\}_{j=1}^n, \{\tau_j\}_{j=1}^n)$ and x is supported on N in the expansion using basis $(\{g_k\}_{k=1}^n, \{\omega_k\}_{k=1}^n)$, then $x = 0$.

We note that Inequality (5) will not give Inequality (2) as p-adic norm is not given using p-adic inner product.

We end the paper with an important open question. Let \mathcal{H} be a finite dimensional Hilbert space. Given an orthonormal basis $\{\tau_j\}_{j=1}^n$ for \mathcal{H} , the **(finite) Shannon entropy** at a point $h \in \mathcal{H}_\tau$ is defined as

$$S_\tau(h) := - \sum_{j=1}^n |\langle h, \tau_j \rangle|^2 \log |\langle h, \tau_j \rangle|^2 \geq 0,$$

where $\mathcal{H}_\tau := \{h \in \mathcal{H} : \|h\| = 1, \langle h, \tau_j \rangle \neq 0, 1 \leq j \leq n\}$ [2]. In 1983, Deutsch derived following uncertainty principle for Shannon entropy which is fundamental to several developments in Mathematics and Physics [2].

Theorem 3.5. [2] (*Deutsch Uncertainty Principle*) Let $\{\tau_j\}_{j=1}^n, \{\omega_j\}_{j=1}^n$ be two orthonormal bases for a finite dimensional Hilbert space \mathcal{H} . Then

$$(8) \quad 2 \log n \geq S_\tau(h) + S_\omega(h) \geq -2 \log \left(\frac{1 + \max_{1 \leq j, k \leq n} |\langle \tau_j, \omega_k \rangle|}{2} \right) \geq 0, \quad \forall h \in \mathcal{H}_\tau.$$

Let $\{\tau_j\}_{j=1}^n$ be a p-adic orthonormal basis for a p-adic Hilbert space \mathcal{X} . Given a p-adic orthonormal basis $\{\tau_j\}_{j=1}^n$ for \mathcal{X} , the **(finite) p-adic Shannon entropy** at a point $x \in \mathcal{X}_\tau$ is defined as

$$S_\tau(x) := - \sum_{j=1}^n |\langle x, \tau_j \rangle|^2 \log |\langle x, \tau_j \rangle|^2 \geq 0,$$

where $\mathcal{X}_\tau := \{x \in \mathcal{X} : \|x\| = 1, \langle x, \tau_j \rangle \neq 0, 1 \leq j \leq n\}$. We then have the following problem.

Question 3.6. What is the p-adic version of Deutsch uncertainty principle (8)?

It has been observed very recently [10] that using Buzano inequality, (which we state below) one can give a simple proof of Inequality (8).

Theorem 3.7. [1, 3, 13] (*Buzano Inequality*) Let \mathcal{H} be a Hilbert space. Then

$$(9) \quad |\langle \tau, h \rangle \langle h, \omega \rangle| \leq \frac{\|h\|^2 (|\langle \tau, \omega \rangle| + \|\tau\| \|\omega\|)}{2}, \quad \forall h, \tau, \omega \in \mathcal{H}.$$

As Inequality (9) easily gives Inequality (8), we formulate following problem whose solution will give a p-adic version of Inequality (8).

Question 3.8. What is the p-adic version of Buzano Inequality (9)?

We note that there is an improvement of Inequality (8) due to Maassen and Uffink in 1988 [9] motivated from the conjecture by Kraus [8] made in 1987 (using Riesz-Thorin interpolation), whose p-adic version is also not known.

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